

Supplemental table 2. Peripapillary average retinal nerve fiber layer and ganglion cell-inner plexiform layer thickness, and visual field parameters according to different type of medication

		Using SSRI		P value	Using SNRI		P value	Using antipsychotics		P value
		No	Yes		No	Yes		No	Yes	
RNFL thickness, μm	Average	92.5 $\pm$ 7.9	94.6 $\pm$ 7.8	0.378	93.5 $\pm$ 7.3	95.4 $\pm$ 10.3	0.501	93.2 $\pm$ 7.2	96.6 $\pm$ 10.3	0.252
GCIPL thickness, μm	Average	79.0 $\pm$ 6.6	82.9 $\pm$ 5.6	0.033	81.5 $\pm$ 6.5	81.9 $\pm$ 4.8	0.858	81.6 $\pm$ 6.1	81.4 $\pm$ 7.1	0.955
	Minimum	75.2 $\pm$ 9.1	78.8 $\pm$ 5.4	0.095	77.5 $\pm$ 7.3	77.8 $\pm$ 5.9	0.908	77.9 $\pm$ 7.3	76.1 $\pm$ 5.6	0.507
Visual field	MD	-2.0 $\pm$ 2.2	-2.5 $\pm$ 1.9	0.427	-2.3 $\pm$ 2.0	-2.7 $\pm$ 1.9	0.639	-2.3 $\pm$ 1.9	-2.6 $\pm$ 2.1	0.698
	PSD	1.7 $\pm$ 0.4	1.9 $\pm$ 0.5	0.273	1.9 $\pm$ 0.5	1.7 $\pm$ 0.4	0.297	1.8 $\pm$ 0.4	2.0 $\pm$ 0.5	0.296

Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor, SSRI